

Spring-in characteristics of thermoplastic composites with glass fiber fabric reinforcement

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1 Abstract

This paper introduces spring-in characteristics of composites with glass fiber fabric reinforcement. These composites become more important for automotive lightweight parts. After heating over melting temperature they are formable several times but forming processes can lead to distortions like spring-in or spring-back. They depend on a wide variety of process parameters, like geometry, pressure, velocity, process temperature and friction. These parameters influence the interply-slip, the primary deformation mode for bending of multilayered sheets. Furthermore they lead to different cooling behavior. Fiber reinforced thermoplastic have anisotropic thermal expansion coefficients. Varying process temperatures influence the resulting bending angle due to this anisotropy. The distortions may cause problems during assembly. For this, the influence of named parameters on spring-in behavior was analyzed with a die bending test. The friction between metal tools and composites were investigated with a separated model test.

The test results show that the spring-in behavior as well as the friction behavior is complex. The influence of pressure and tool temperature on resulting bending angles seems to be nearly linear. But varying the velocity of the punch leads to increasing or decreasing bending angles. It depends on the bending radii.

The friction test results show that the different process parameters influence each other. If the tools are heated to 50 °C, increasing velocities result in increasing friction coefficients. But heating the tools to 150 °C leads to decreasing friction coefficients with increasing velocities for example.

2 Introduction

With the focus on fast and cost efficient production methods for automotive lightweight parts, fiber reinforced thermoplastics become more important and replaces reinforced thermosets. After heating over melting temperature they are formable several times. This enables to use semi-finished products in the form of pre-consolidated sheets. They can be reheated and processed using known stamping methods with suitable modifications.

Manufacturing processes can lead to distortions like spring-in due to anisotropic material properties. Those shape distortions may cause problems during assembly, if the resulting dimensions differ too much from their specified values [1].

Spring-in depends on a wide variety of process parameters, like geometry, pressure, velocity and process temperature. Friction also plays an important role in forming processes of thermoplastic laminates [2]. It occurs wherever the laminate is in contact with another surface, such as the die or the blankholder [3]. For this, friction influences the amount of stress that is lead into the fiber-reinforced thermoplastic. This can help to reduce wrinkling, as well as to cause unwanted distortions.

In this work the influence of different parameters on spring-in was analyzed with a die bending test to derive suggestions for tool and process modifications. The friction between composites and metal tools are mainly influenced by the process parameters temperature, normal pressure and sliding velocity [4] [5]. This behavior was analyzed with a separate test model and its results were integrated in the interpretation of the die bending test results.

The investigated material is a glass fiber reinforced polyamide-66 with three layers of twill fabric. Polyamide-6 and polyamide-66 are frequently used

matrix materials for automotive parts made of composite sheets.

Many studies [2, 4, 5, 6, 10-15] of the frictional behavior, interply as well as tool-ply, and manufacturing distortions focused on glass/polypropylene composites.

The experiments that are investigated in this work are based on glass/polyamide composites to obtain quantitative results for this material. Afterwards qualitative test results are compared to the findings of other authors studying glass/polypropylene composites.

Assuming that inter-ply friction or rather interply-slip is one of the main factors when bending multilayered reinforced plastics, this work focuses on the temperature dependency of this mechanism as a reason of increasing or decreasing viscosity values. In Addition, cooling behavior of the material was recorded for different tool temperatures during the tests.

3 Spring-in and friction characteristics

Residual stresses in reinforced thermoplastics after manufacturing process can lead to unwanted shape distortions. When forming a sheet to a single curve the residual bending angle can differ from the nominal angle of the mould (Fig.1).

Salomi et al. [6] and Han et al. [1] propose an analytical equation (1) to predict the residual bending angle after forming. It is based on the assumption that shape distortion depends on the thermal contraction during cooling the material from forming temperature to room temperature due to anisotropic thermal coefficients. This equation is a simplification of those introduced by Radford [7] that also considers the chemical reaction of thermoset matrices.

$$\Delta\theta = \frac{(\theta-180)(\alpha_l-\alpha_t)\Delta T}{1+\alpha_t \Delta T} \quad (1)$$

$\Delta\theta$ is the spring-in angle; θ is the mould angle; α_l is the longitudinal coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE); α_t is the through-thickness coefficient of thermal expansion; ΔT is the change in temperature.

The coefficients of thermal expansions polyamide-66 and e-glass are reported in table 1.

Salomi et al. [6] and Lee et al. [8] assume that the

in-plane CTE is dominated by the fiber reinforcement and the through-thickness CTE is dominated by the matrix system. According to this assumption the values in table 1 show that the through-thickness coefficient of the composite has to be much higher than the in-plane coefficient. For this, equation (1) would always result in decreasing bending angles (-) (Fig.1). This effect is called spring-in.

[6] shows a significant deviation of experimental results and theoretical calculation of resulting bending angles. For this reason, there has to be more factors of influence. Authors modified the equation to account for CTE variations at the corner due to fibers wrinkling and inhomogeneous fibers distribution and got a better fit of experimental results. Further factors of influence for spring-in characteristics and deviations between theoretical and test results could be tool-part interactions, crystallization behavior or dwelltime for example. They account for stress increase or relaxation during the process.

First experimental results of the die bending test of this work also show decreasing bending angles (spring-in) but additionally increasing bending angles (spring-forward) while varying process parameters.

As mentioned before, spring-forward effect that is defined as a 'positive angular deviation' (+) (Fig.1) cannot be described by equation (1).

In spite of this, the spring-forward phenomenon will also lead back to temperature dependencies due to their influence to the forming mechanisms of thermoplastic composites. The most important ones are interply-slip and shear deformation of woven fabrics. Interply-slip is the primary deformation mode for bending of multilayered sheets (Fig.1) [9]. If the polymer matrix cools down below its molding temperature, interply-slip is suppressed (completely or separately). Resulting tensile stresses at the outside radius of the formed sheet cause 'positive angular deviation' (+).

Friction between separated layers of a sheet also affects interplay-slip. Many authors refer to Stribeck curve (Fig.2) to explain this effect. This curve describes the amount of friction forces plotted against the Hersey number (2) in case of hydrodynamic lubrication.

$$H = \frac{\eta \times U}{N} \quad (2)$$

The Hersey number (H) considers the influence of viscosity (η), sliding velocity (U) and normal pressure (N) on liquid film thickness or the amount of melted polymer between several layers, respectively.

According to the Hersey number friction forces are proportional to matrix viscosity and sliding velocity and inversely proportional to normal pressure. Matrix viscosity in turn is also dependent on sliding velocity and actual matrix temperature.

For this reason spring-in characteristics of fiber reinforced thermoplastics are complex. Different factors of influence interact with each other. So, the cooling behavior from forming temperature to room temperature of formed parts has to be controlled exactly to get reproducible parts.

In addition to interply friction, tool-ply friction can also affect spring-in phenomenon due to stresses at the outer surfaces of the material. Furthermore friction forces determine required forming forces and for this the required press capacity.

Otherwise, friction forces are desired to generate in-plane forces preventing unwanted fabric wrinkling. During the forming process in-plane forces are developed by friction between blank-holder and composite. If the in-plane forces are too low, wrinkling occurs. On the other hand high in-plane forces can result in damage of the material. [10] Controlling friction forces in manufacturing processes requires the understanding of different types of friction and their factors of influence.

The friction also depends on process temperatures. If the polymer matrix plastifies, a thin liquid film is formed between composite and tool surface. While cooling down, the polymer matrix becomes solid. Due to its state of aggregation there are two types of friction, hydrodynamic and coulomb friction. Coulomb friction occurs between dry surfaces. The friction law states that friction forces are proportional to normal force and independent of sliding velocity. With increasing temperature and decreasing matrix viscosity combined with an increase of the normal pressure hydrodynamic friction can shift to direct coulomb friction of the fibers with the tool [11]. At high temperatures

friction between reinforced thermoplastics and metal tools are a combination of both types of friction. [4] Hydrodynamic friction can be explained using the Stribeck curve (Fig. 2), again. So, this type of friction is dependent on sliding velocity in contrast to coulomb friction.

4 Model tests

4.1 Friction test

The friction behavior between composites and metal tools has been investigated with a pull-out and a pull-through test according to [4] [12]. It represents friction contact on both sides of the sheet. In this work the test procedure is non-isothermal to meet realistic conditions. The schematic test setup is shown in Fig. 3. At first the organic sheet is heated with a contact heating unit and then placed between two hydraulically controlled pressure plates that are heatable to 150 °C. The test setup is fitted to a universal testing machine. This enables to control the pullout velocity and to measure the pull-out force that corresponds to double friction force because of two contact areas (Fig. 3). The transfer between the heating unit and the testing machine is performed by an operator. The transfer time was kept constant for every test specimen.

The friction tests were conducted under variation of the temperatures of the sheet and the pressure plates, the normal pressure and pullout velocity. The pressure plates are made of steel with a smooth surface. Within further experimental series the influence of other materials and surfaces finishes has also been investigated. The different test conditions are listed in table 2.

During the tests the required pull-out forces are plotted against the pull-out length of the sheet. The friction force (F_R) that is equal to the half pull-out force is divided by the normal force (F_N) to determine the friction coefficient (μ) according to equation (3). The normal force is calculated by the hydraulic pressure (p_N) multiplied by the contact area (A_P) between the pressure plates and the organic sheet (eq. 4).

$$\mu = \frac{F_R}{2 \times F_N} \quad (3)$$

$$F_N = p_N \times A_P \quad (4)$$

As mentioned, there are two methods for the friction test, the pull-out test and the pull-through test (Fig.3). The pull-through test has been chosen for most of the tests in this work. For higher temperatures of the sheet and the plates in combination with increasing normal pressure the pull-out test has been used to get a better repeatability for this parameter values.

For the pull-out tests the friction coefficients have been calculated considering the continuously decreasing contact area with increasing displacement of the sheet.

Experiments have been done with three sheet temperatures: 23 °C (*room temperature (RT*)), 200 °C and 300 °C.

The melting temperature of polyamide-66 is 260 °C. For this the sheet is heated up to 300 °C in the contact heating unit to ensure a sheet temperature of about 260 °C at the beginning of the friction test. The heating temperature of 200 °C is chosen to realize a testing temperature of 160 °C that represents conditions between glass transition temperature of 70 °C and softening temperature of 220 °C.

Test results and discussion

Result curves of friction tests typically show an initial peak force followed by a steady state situation. Relative movement between the sheet and the pressure plates cannot occur until the pull-out force overcomes the initial peak. After that the required forces to hold up the relative movement are lower. The different situations are described by the static and dynamic friction coefficient. In this work the dynamic friction coefficients will be considered. Figure 4 shows coefficient of friction vs. displacement curves of different sheet temperatures. Only for a sheet temperature of 300 °C there is a significant difference between the static and dynamic friction coefficient. At sheet temperatures of 200 °C and room temperature there is no difference between them. Figure 4 also shows that the friction coefficient is much higher if the polymer matrix is melted. The contact area increases due to the liquid polyamide. For this, van der Waals forces increase. Furthermore adhesive bonds can occur when the polymer cools down.

One method to reduce the friction forces are heated

tools. This slows the rate at which the polymer cools down and remains as a liquid film between the sheet and the tool for a longer time. Figure 5 shows that the friction coefficients decrease if the temperature of pressure plates increases. This behavior has also been detected for the sheet temperature of 200 °C because the material remains above its softening temperature for a longer time. For this the required forces to deform the roughness profile of its surfaces are much lower.

The variation of sliding velocity only results in different friction coefficients for the sheet temperature of 300 °C. At 200 °C there is no influence of sliding velocity to friction forces. Also increasing normal pressures don't result in different friction coefficients according to Coulomb's friction law.

At 300 °C the friction coefficients either decrease or increase with increasing sliding velocity dependent on normal pressure and tool temperature (Fig. 5).

If the tools are heated to 150 °C friction coefficients increase with increasing sliding velocities and decreasing normal pressures (cp. 2,2 MPa and 4 MPa). This indicates for hydrodynamic lubrication according to Stribeck curve (Fig. 2). [2, 4, 5, 10, 12, 14, 15] show similar test results for glass/polypropylene composites.

At higher normal pressures (6 MPa) increasing velocities result in decreasing friction coefficients. According to equation (2) the Hersey number decreases with increasing normal pressure. For this there could be a shift from hydrodynamic to elasto-hydrodynamic lubrication (Fig. 2). Furthermore the fluid film may break down due to high pressures. In this case the glass fibers get into contact with the tools surfaces and there is a combination of hydrodynamic and coulomb friction as explained by [4].

Experiments with a tool temperature of 50 °C also result in decreasing friction coefficients with increasing sliding velocity. But the coefficients are much higher. Contacting the tool surfaces, the polymer matrix cools down and solidifies. For this, the polymer and the tools surface may bond, especially at slow relative velocities. This bond has to be broken and the solidified polyamide has to be deformed.

The comparison of different materials shows that

aluminum tools reduce friction forces compared to tools made of steel (Fig. 6) but in some cases they affect the surface structure of the sheets. Rougher surfaces result in increasing friction coefficients (Fig. 6) for a sheet temperature of 200 °C. The roughness peaks deform the polymer matrix and friction forces increase. Test results for a sheet temperature of 300 °C mostly lead to decreasing friction coefficients. The rough surface has more gaps where the polymer can accumulate and build-up a 'lubricating film' that decreases the friction forces.

4.2 Die bending test

Spring-in characteristics have been tested with a simple die bending test that bends a small sheet to an angle of 90 degrees (Fig. 1). To characterize the temperature dependence, the tools are heatable to 100 °C to influence the cooling rate of the sheet. [1] shows a similar setup.

The test setup, consisting of a die and a constrained punch, is fitted to a universal testing machine. The bending test is divided into three steps: closing, pressure build-up and dwelling (Fig. 7.). Prior to that the sheet is heated to 350 °C with a contact heating unit and then transferred into the die by an operator. Until the beginning of the closing process the temperature of the sheet decreases to 280 °C.

Areas that are in contact with the punch first, may cool down before the forming tools are completely closed. For this, the punch geometry (bending radius), its velocity and temperature affect the interply-slip. Furthermore, the relative movement between several plies of the composite depends on the closing pressure. For this the tests were conducted under variation of different process parameters that are listed in table 3. After removal and completed cooling down the bending angles of the test specimens are measured with a micrometer caliper. The angles are captured at three different points over the width and an average value is calculated.

The changes in temperature over closing time are reported for different tool temperatures, pressures and velocities to point out its influence to the cooling rate of the sheet. The temperature was measured using an infrared thermometer at the contact area between the sheet and the radius of the punch.

Test results and discussion

The die bending tests result in decreasing bending angles, if the tools are heated. Figure 8 shows a significant spring-in behavior for a tool temperature of 100 °C. Additionally, increasing velocities of the punch mainly result in decreasing bending angle (Fig. 9). For lower bending radii this behavior applies for velocities of 5 mm/s and 10 mm/s, only. The test with low velocities and small bending radii lead to decreasing bending angles.

Furthermore, test results show a linear dependency of bending angles to forming pressure for all bending radii (Fig. 10). Increasing forming pressure causes positive angular deviations.

As mentioned before, interply-slip is one of the most important forming mechanisms when bending a multilayered sheet. This mechanism benefits from low matrix viscosity and for this from high temperatures. It is assumed that suppressing the interply-slip before the end of the forming process leads to spring-forward. Therefore, the polymer matrix needs to stay plastified till then.

Figure 11 shows the change in temperature over process time. The velocity is 0,5 mm/s and the pressure is 3 MPa (13 kN). The sheet temperature is 280 °C (1) at the beginning of the forming process. It decreases to 210 °C (2) until the tools are closed and the consolidation pressure of 3MPa is reached. For this, the polymer cools down below its melting temperature before the tools are closed completely. For higher velocities (5 mm/s and 10 mm/s) the temperature is about 260 °C. Heating the tools slows down the cooling rate and the sheet temperature after pressure build-up increases to 270 °C.

Increasing forming pressure has no dependence on the cooling rate but on the resulting bending angles. For this, increasing pressure or forming force lead to higher friction force between several layers. Its relative movement will be suppressed and this results in spring-forward (Fig. 10).

Figure 9 shows that increasing bending radii lead to decreasing bending angles for a velocity of 10 mm/s. In contrast, tests with a low velocity of 0,5 mm/s show a behavior in opposite direction. If the punch velocity is 0,5 mm/s the sheet cools down below its melting temperature before the tools are closed completely (Fig. 11). The assumption that this behavior leads to spring-forward due to suppressed

interply-slip does not apply.

The inner and outer bending radii of the tools differ due to the thickness of the sheet. To adjust this difference the several layers of the sheet have to slide over each other. This interply-slip has to occur along the whole width of the sheet. A smaller bending radius leads to a smaller area cooled down by the punch and therefore to smaller cooling rates until the tools are closed.

At higher velocities, the forming pressure is reached earlier and the friction forces between the layers increase. Interply-slip is more difficult and there is a shift from spring-in to spring-forward.

5 Discussion

Die bending tests of fiber reinforced thermoplastics show that spring-in and spring-forward phenomenon occur varying different process parameters. The dependence on velocity for example, varies for different bending radii. Therefore, consistent suggestions for tool design cannot be given. The dependence on forming pressure and tool temperature seems to be nearly linear, though. For this, the variation of these process parameters can help to achieve a final 90° shape.

[1] [6] increased the mould angle to 92° to adjust negative angle deviations and achieve a final 90° V-shape. The die bending test in this work also results in positive angular deviations. In this case the mould angle has to be decreased.

The simplest way to influence the resulting bending angle is to heat up the tools. With regard to the findings of the friction test, this will also result in decreasing friction forces, and stresses in the outer surface of the sheet will be reduced.

Process parameters that have a great influence on friction forces also have a great influence on interply-slip and thermal shrinkage. These parameters are velocity, pressure and temperature. To analyze the dependence of tool-ply friction to spring-in behavior, the friction forces have to be increased by another parameter. For this, tools with rougher surface finishes can be used in further studies.

Fig.1. Spring-in and interply-slip of a multilayered sheet

	PA 66	E-glass
Coefficient of thermal expansion [$\frac{10^{-6}}{K}$]	85	5

Table 1: Coefficients of thermal expansion

Fig. 2. Stribeck Curve [10]

Fig. 3. Friction test setup

Parameter	Values			Unit
	2,2	4	6	
P_N	2,2	4	6	MPa
v	0,5	5	10	$\frac{\text{mm}}{\text{s}}$
T_{sheet}	RT*	200	300	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
T_{plates}	RT*	50	150	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
material	steel	aluminium		-
surface finish	smooth	rough		-

*RT = room temperature

Table 2: Friction test parameter

Fig. 4: Static and dynamic friction

Fig. 5: Summary of experimental results for steady state friction

Fig.6. Friction coefficient depending on tool material and surface finish

Parameter	Values				Unit
p_N	3	5	7		MPa
v	0,5	5	10		$\frac{mm}{s}$
R	2	6	10	14	mm
T_{Punch}	RT*	50	100		°C
T_{Die}	RT*	50	100		°C
T_{Sheet}	280				°C
t_H	5				s
*RT = room temperature					

Table 3: Die bending test parameter

Fig.7. Temperature vs. time curve of bending test

Fig.8. Bending angle depending on tool temperature

Fig.9. Bending angle depending on radius and velocity

Fig.10. Bending angle depending on radius and pressure

6 Conclusion

The conducted studies analyze the friction and spring-in behavior of glass fiber reinforced polyamide-66 to derive suggestions for tool design and process criteria.

Shape deformations have a high dependence on process temperatures and cooling rates. Understanding this effect helps to control the stamp forming process.

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